

State of the Art Report for *A New Methodological Approach to Analyze Human Roles in Human-Robot Interaction Scenarios*

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Purpose:

This report is written for the purpose of introducing three papers that look into the state of the art for the field of Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) and its implications on society. More specifically, the HRI has to do with robots that deliver packages in the last-mile and their development alongside humans. This is provided for the paper *A New Methodological Approach to Analyze Human Roles in Human-Robot Interaction Scenarios* and for any uses that the authors of this paper deem suitable.

Method:

The papers that are reported were searched for using the following criteria. One, the paper had to propose or infer on a future research or future problems that Human-Robot Interaction with last-mile delivery robots may face when it is implemented with daily life. Two, the paper had to mention an insight or provide a unique perspective on the roles that humans can have when working with robots in the package delivery and distribution industry. Three, the sources of the paper had to be credible.

These papers were searched using the Google Scholar search engine using key words such as "HRI," "last-mile," "delivery," and "robot." Various papers were read and looked through and the three most relevant ones were chosen.

Introduction to the Three Papers:

1. *An Open-Source Framework Last Mile Delivery with Heterogeneous Robots*

The most technical paper of the three. Topic is over an experiment that is very similar to one carried out by researchers in the Mobile Robotics group in the UPC-IRI (ONA). The most relevant section mentions the necessity for a human companion and remote operators with the delivery robot.

2. *Autonomous ground vehicles in urban last-mile delivery – an exploration of the implementation feasibility and consumer's acceptance*

This paper, as well as the third one, looks more into the economic and business possibilities of last-mile delivery robots. The researcher here uses two approaches and conducted multiple studies to see whether or not deliveries being done by robots will be economically viable and socially accepted in the near future.

3. *Autonomous Delivery Robots: A Literature Review*

The studies done for this paper come from a review of the state of the art of delivery robots. Using this, the researcher comes up with conclusions on the business opportunities of delivery robots and their possible integration with human roles.

An Open-Source Framework Last Mile Delivery with Heterogeneous Robots

https://repositories.lib.utexas.edu/bitstream/handle/2152/84819/SMADS_AAAI_SSS_2021.pdf?sequence=2

Asha Kailin Jain, Maxwell Svetlik, Nicholas Machak, Kavan Singh Sikand, Cem Karamanli, Kaiyu Zhou, Justin Hart, Joydeep Biswas, Luis Sentis, Junfeng Jiao

Summary:

This research team at the University of Texas at Austin created the Short to Medium Range Autonomous Delivery System (SMADS). It consists of a last-mile delivery robot which is able to deliver small packages to users who input a location in an associated mobile application. The app has a graphical user interface which shows where the robot is on a map and confirms the pickup. Another application exists for managers of the robot to be able to supervise the robot. Commands from the management app are translated into ROS-level commands for the robot. A SMADS Management Server exists to handle order requests and assign/queue robots to deliveries. They tested the use of SMADS on the campus of UT Austin where they opened deliveries to external customers. The robots were accompanied by human supervisors in order to ensure their functionality.

The following is relating to the robot's performance in the environment of the UT Austin campus. The robot ran into some problems when it would intermittently disconnect from the Wifi since its connection to the mobile application ran through a Wifi connection. Also, problems were encountered in some cases when the robot would approach a physical barrier; this would require a physical intervention by the human supervisor. The robot also ran into problems when it encountered dynamic obstacles such as pedestrians or cyclists. The navigation through unexpected obstacles was one of the major challenges faced during the experiments.

Thoughts:

This paper's experiment is extremely similar to the one being done at IRI with ONA. In this case though, the mobile application is further developed and a key piece of the project. This paper shows that work still needs to be done in order to make last-mile delivery robots viable in everyday life. There still exists the challenge of the robot being able to avoid expected and unexpected obstacles safely. Also the robot must have a variety of ways it can move in order to adjust itself to the changing urban environment. External customers of the robot's services also need to be properly informed about how the robot functions in order to ensure a safe and complete delivery. Eventually, the goal should be to have the delivery robot unaccompanied and be able to complete deliveries in a manner that is more economical and efficient than a delivery carried out by a human.

Autonomous ground vehicles in urban last-mile delivery – an exploration of the implementation feasibility and consumer's acceptance

<https://repositorio.ucp.pt/handle/10400.14/29253>

Daniel Barthuly

Summary:

The main objective of this paper is to look into the human-robot acceptance of what Barthuly calls autonomous ground vehicles (AGVs) which in this case refers to last-mile delivery robots. He looks at the viability of the implementation of last-mile delivery robots into the urban space by looking at two distinct perspectives. One: the technological viability of the robot by looking at industry data and interviewing experts. Two: the consumer's acceptance of the robot by conducting an online survey and running statistical analysis on the responses.

Some of the relevant conclusions that Barthuly makes are as follows. He says that a fully autonomous robot is not at this time feasible for the industry. The relatively low cost of human labor versus the high costs of creating and implementing this high level technology results in a hybrid robot-human delivery system being more viable. Also it is noted that having the robots operate on sidewalks rather than on roads might be more feasible since there are less restrictions and regulations in sidewalks. Regarding the consumer opinion on last-mile delivery robots in sidewalks, most people had a positive attitude towards the topic. The concern was not high for the safety and the guarantee of delivery of the robots.

Thoughts:

I believe this paper gives a good analysis on the viability of the business of last-mile delivery robots. Realistically for these robots to become prominent in the daily lives of urban areas, it needs to be economically feasible for companies to deliver their objects through these robots rather than through human workers. The corporations will take whichever option is more economical. Therefore, it makes sense that these robots will probably not be prominent for another while until the technology improves and is easier to mass produce using an economy of scale. Also, one can note that developing countries may not have access for this technology until much after it becomes integrated in developed countries that have accepted it. Generally, it is a good note that most people are open to having delivery robots in urban spaces. This opinion will allow for less friction when the robots are first being implemented into urban areas around the world.

Autonomous Delivery Robots: A Literature Review

<https://deliverypdf.ssrn.com/delivery.php?ID=820106101027028101085074105124064122005089089042053026107004014061048004060014029117011123010072065086028080115023006065100029097004110070005007007074080034017099067090014037053114066072076044002036105103008040016089122118124102106126084086101126122124105116079003096080093126088021104094111&EXT=pdf&INDEX=TRUE>

Mokter Hossain

Summary:

In the paper, Hossain looks into what he calls Autonomous delivery robots (ADRs), which can be considered for this purpose as last-mile delivery robots, and the potential market for them. Hossain claims that ADRs will in the near future create a huge market which he mentions is expected to reach US\$55 billion by 2026 with an estimated annual growth rate of 20.4%. A key factor to the implementation of ADRs would be the consumer acceptance of them which largely depends on the consumer demographics. Another key factor in making ADRs widespread is the development of technology such as integrating AI and the blockchain with the network of delivery robots in order to ensure the safety of each delivery.

Thoughts:

Hossain provides a very compelling and comprehensive argument towards the high potential of last-mile delivery robots and their market in the future. He does acknowledge that there are some major challenges that these robots must face before it is feasible that they are integrated into our society. As long as there is development of this technology and of the robot, eventually these robots will be viable and will make a huge economic impact on current delivery systems and commerce.